

TEACHERS' WORKING CONDITION IN THE NEW NORMAL: A GROUNDWORK FOR A PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PLAN IN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS DIVISION OF ZAMBALES PHILIPPINES

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Abstract

An investigation of the existing teachers' working condition in the 'new normal at Senior High Schools (SHS) in the Division of Zambales, Philippines during the school year 2022-2023 was the foremost aim of the present study. The respondents were the Secondary School Heads and their respective Senior High School Teachers from the thirteen Districts of Department of Education (DepEd) Schools Division of Zambales. The present study utilized a descriptive research design; used a survey questionnaire as instrument for data gathering; and employed descriptive and inferential statistics for data analysis. The study found that the school heads are male, middle aged adults, Principal II, Master's Degree holders with Doctorate units, and have been serving for two and a half decades while the SHS teachers are female, young adults, Teacher II, Baccalaureate Degree holders with Master's units, and serving as professional teachers for less than a decade. The teachers' working condition that always exist based on school heads' perception was human capital most expressly on having a school head who is a role model for the work group while the teachers perceived that social capital working condition exist in Senior High Schools specifically focused on commitment on education and towards moral-ethical perspective on work. An Enhancement Plan was formulated aimed to further improve Senior High School teachers' working condition.

Keywords: Senior High Schools, School Heads, Teacher, Working Condition, New Normal.

INTRODUCTION

The work environment in which people work is all the aspects of the work and workplace condition may affect productivity gains (World Economic Forum, 2020); achieving quality education for all (UNESCO, 2008); crucial for retaining well qualified teachers (OECD, 2019). Primary and secondary schools in the Philippines have developed a unique working condition in the post COVID19 pandemic and during the 'new normal' in the education setting. School administrators and educators are fighting to nurture and sustain school community and working condition conducive for their learners, allows more professional development to educators; and that parents and other stakeholders be more involved.

In the realization to the aims of the Senior High Schools to equip learners with skills that will better prepare them for the future whether it be in employment, entrepreneurship, skills development, and higher education (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), according to Cogal (2019); and Dizon Jr. (2021) it is crucial to consider the role of leaders in the 21st century to set up in education system urgently needed to provide proper support and coordination for workers; adaptive to the existing working condition and enriching the main or dominant culture in the institution. The Department of Education Task Force Covid19 (DTFC) Memo 57, s.2020 and in the studies of Dizon, et al. (2021); and Cariño & de Guzman (2023) emphasized that

effective educational program must focus on the improvement of teaching and learning condition and environment.

Ideally, school administrators and teachers prefers to function and maintain a conducive work environment in which they can be able to attain their goals - personal, professional and for their learners. Avoids toxic culture and environment which can tarnish their daily plans, perception, character and behavior. The research theme on working condition and environment are enormously important among teachers of basic education, particularly the Senior High Schools. A deeper investigation will paved the way to appreciating and understanding teachers' continuous pursuit to deliver quality and best education to learners in the province of Zambales, Philippines amidst the experienced pandemic and its long-lasting effect.

The variables on working conditions of the present study are anchored on Mason & Poyatos Matas' (2015) components of capital model. The researcher aspires to contribute to a broader knowledge in the variables presented. There is scarcity of research in the Senior High School levels in the Division of Zambales that explores working conditions towards school efficiency and empowerment in the new normal educational landscape.

The result of this study would provide empirical data on Senior High School teachers on the existing working conditions that can further enhance teaching and learning, that can contribute to their professional growth, making them more empowered teachers in the 'new normal'. Results of the present study will provide the School Administrators an understanding of teachers' working condition in the Division of Zambales which is an important tool in addressing teachers; concerns and needs; and maintaining focus on student learning. Moreover, this study would provide them the necessary and clear ideas in enhancing their managerial and leadership skills; development plans; and ways to improve schools' forking conditions in terms of human capital, social capital, and structural capital. Schools with acceptable working conditions; and child friendly and welcoming environment to parents and other stakeholders members have an easier time creating successful partnership program and sustaining engagement.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the teachers' working condition at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales, Philippines in the 'new normal' set-up in the country's Basic Education. Specifically, the study answered the following specific questions:

1. How may the profile of the Senior High School Head and Senior High Teacher respondents be described as to: gender, age, highest educational attainment, length of service, and position/designation?
2. How may the Senior High School Head and Senior High Teacher-respondents describe the teachers' working conditions in terms of Human Capital, Social Capital, and Structural Capital?
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers' working condition when grouped according to school head respondents' profile?

4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of teachers' working condition when grouped according to senior high teacher-respondents' profile?
5. What Proposed Enhancement Plan aimed to further nurture the preferred school culture, improve teachers' working condition and policy development at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales in the New Normal?

MATERIALS & METHODS

The researcher used a descriptive design of research concerned mainly with describing SHS teachers' working condition as they are without manipulation of what is being observed. For McCombes (2022), quantitative analysis aims to interpret the data collected for the phenomenon through numeric variables and statistics. Quantitative analysis is based on describing and interpreting objects statistically and with numbers. The present study investigated and described the existing teachers' working condition at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales. It aims to ascertain how basic educational institution described their work environment in terms of human, social and structural conditions.

The respondents are 225 teachers (sample size for teachers was determined using the Slovin formula) and a total population of 30 principals/school heads. They are all employed during the school year 2022-2023 in 32 Public Secondary Schools, Senior High School Department of DepEd, Division of Zambales (Sta. Cruz, Candelaria, Masinloc, Palauig, Iba, Botolan, Cabangan, San Felipe, San Narciso, San Antonio, San Marcelino, Castillejos and Subic Districts).

The main instrument for data gathering was survey questionnaire. According to Nalicat & de Guzman (2022) survey questionnaire is a research instrument that consists objective questions that are intended to gain extensive information from respondents. Such questions are used to collect numerical data that can be used for statistical analysis. Part 1 of the instrument was obtained personal information about the respondents on areas such as gender, age, highest educational attainment, designation, length of service and academic position. included items/indicators that assessed preferred school culture. Mason & Poyatos Matas' (2015, also discussed in Masoom, 2021 and Nkambule, 2022) components of Capital Model such as Human Capital, Social Capital, and Structural Capital were utilized to identify and describe the working conditions of SHS teachers of the present study (Second part of the instrument). This part has a total of 45 indicators. Each of the components has 15 indicators each. The answers of the respondents are within a 4-point scale ranging from (4) Always, (3) Frequent, (2) Sometimes; and (1) Never.

The instrument in its first draft was presented to the experts on the field of school management and administration of PRMSU Graduate School for validity purpose. Their ideas, suggestions and corrections were sought in terms of the extent of clarity, consistency, and suitability. The corrections/revisions were carried on in finalizing the research instrument. The conduct of a pilot test is necessary for the research instrument's test of reliability. The pilot test was conducted among the principal and teachers at Laboratory High School Department of

PRMSU, Iba, Zambales. Cronbach’s alpha was computed to test the reliability of the responses in the pilot test. The cronbach's alpha values are Human Capital (0.973), Social Capital (0.975), and Structural Capital (0.925). Qualitative interpretation for each variable is Excellent.

The researcher sought in March, 2023 the approval to administer the survey questionnaire to the respondents from Schools Division Superintendent, DepEd Division of Zambales. After securing the permission, the researcher proceeded in the distribution and retrieval of the instrument from the respondents. The respondents were assured of the confidentiality of their responses. Moreover, the researcher made sure that the respondents fully understood the objectives and the benefits of the research. The data gathered were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics (frequency count, percentage and weighted mean, and Analysis of Variance).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of the Senior High School Head and Senior High Teacher-Respondents DepEd Division of Zambales

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Senior High School Heads and Teachers’ Profile

Personal Profile Variables		School Heads		Senior High Teachers	
Gender		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Female		10	33.33	141	62.67
Male		17	56.67	80	35.55
LGBTQ+		3	10.00	4	1.78
Total		30	100.00	225	100.00
Age		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Total		30	100.00	225	100.00
		Mean = 52.43 years old		Mean = 34.71 years old	
Highest Educational Attainment		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Doctors Degree		8	26.67	11	4.88
Master’s w/EdD or PhD Units		10	33.33	20	8.89
Master’s Degree		4	13.33	55	24.44
Bachelor w/ Master’s Unit		7	23.33	102	45.33
Bachelor’s Degree		1	3.33	37	16.44
Total		30	100.00	225	100.00
Length of service		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Total		30	100.00	225	100.00
		Mean = 26.50 years		Mean = 6.70 years	
Designation	Frequency	Percent	Position	Frequency	Percent
Principal IV	5	16.67	Master Teacher III	4	1.78
Principal III	4	13.33	Master Teacher II	7	2.67
Principal II	11	36.67	Master Teacher I	7	2.67
Principal I	4	13.33	Teacher III	63	27.56
Head Teacher	7	20.00	Teacher II	92	40.89
Total	30	100.00	Teacher I	56	24.44
			Total	225	100.00

Gender. Of the 30 school head respondents, there are 17 or 56.67% male, 10 or 33.33% female and 3 (10.00%) are LGBTQ+. World Economic Forum (2020) revealed that in the education sector, it is expected to grow 4% or more in the next decade at all teaching levels. As such, there are many opportunities for men in education.

There are 141 or 62.67% female from the 225 respondents; 80 or 35.33% male; and 4 (1.78%) LGBTQ+. More than half of the teachers employed in the senior high schools are female. Dizon Jr, et al. (2021) found that women in the teaching profession obtained a higher percentage compared to male teachers.

Age. The mean age of the School Head teachers was 52.43 years old. This particular age is classified into middle aged adults by (Ericsson, Feltovich & Prietula, 2006, cited in de Guzman & Ecle, 2019). Moreover, the result of the present study is reliable with the data obtained in the study of de Guzman, et al. (2021) on age profile variables. Their respondents belong the age bracket (36-40) or middle adulthood.

The mean age of the Senior High teachers was 34.71 years old. This particular age is categorized as young adults (Kessler, Brown & Broman, 1981 as cited in Dizon, et al., 2021). Moreover, the result of the present study is consistent with the data obtained in the studies of de Guzman, et al. (2018) and Coching & de Guzman (2023) on age profile variable. Their respondents belong the age bracket (36-40) or young adulthood.

Highest Educational Attainment. Most (10 or 33.33%) of the school head respondents are holders of Masters with doctorate units. de Guzman, et al. (2023) also revealed that majority of the school principal in the Division of Zambales are holders of Master's degree with EdD/PhD units. Whether it is enhancing current capabilities, exploring a new area of expertise, upskilling plays a vital role in better professional opportunities.

The Senior High School teacher-respondents are mostly (102 or 45.33%) Bachelor Degree holders with Master's units. This result is consistent with Bactad, et al. (2021) revealing that most of the teachers are holders of Bachelor Degree with Master's Units. The DepEd Memo No. 050 s2020 on the other hand supports the realization of the departments goal of continuous upskilling and reskilling and through advance studies of teachers that will result in better learning outcomes.

Length of Service. The length of service of the school head respondents is 26.50 years. The principals in the present study have already been in the service as school administrator for a relatively long period of time.

The senior high school teachers have already rendered service in the teaching profession for more than half a decade (6.70 mean years). The DepEd's Hiring for Senior High School (SHS) teaching positions effective School Year 2016-2017 stipulates that one year relevant teaching/industry work-experience is the experience requirement for SHS Qualification Standards. The senior high school teachers in the study of Dizon Jr. (2021) already rendered their service for five years to a decade.

Position/Designation. The school heads are mostly Principal II (11 or 36.67%), followed by Head Teachers and Principals IV respectively. The majority of the school head respondents of their studies are Principal II. Principal appointee facilitate organizational management through coaching, mentoring, and instruction supervision of school staff. The DepEd Memorandum No. 143, s. 2011, shall serve as a mechanism for selecting competent school heads in the public basic education sector.

Most of the SHS teachers (92 or 40.89%) are Teacher II; followed by Teacher III, and Teacher I respectively. Teacher II was also the academic position of the teacher-respondents in the studies of Bactad, et al. (2021). In the DepEd Order No, 019 s.2022 and DepEd Order No. 66 s. 2007, the Department’s Merit Selection Plan ensures that the Department hires the right people for the right job and appoint and promotes teaching, related teaching and non-teaching positions.

2. Perception of School Heads and Senior High Teachers on the Teachers’ Working Condition

2.1. Human Capital

Table 2: Level of Agreement of the School Heads and Senior High Teachers on the Existing Teachers’ Working Condition as to Human Capital

Human Capital	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. My school head strongly considers my values and professional development goals.	3.80	Always	10	3.46	Always	1.5
2. My school head always discusses works issues and concerns with the work group	3.80	Always	10	3.45	Always	5
3. My school head treats me and my coworkers fairly	3.73	Always	14.5	3.43	Always	9.5
4. My school head values my contribution to department's well-being	3.80	Always	10	3.45	Always	5
5. My school head cares about my opinions and suggestions.	3.80	Always	10	3.36	Always	15
6. The school head acknowledges the vulnerabilities of subordinates and actively hears their concerns	3.73	Always	14.5	3.42	Always	11.5
7. My school head maintains gives out a fair, effective and efficient management of school operations.	3.83	Always	6	3.45	Always	5

8. The school supports my instructional needs by providing opportunities for professional growth.	3.77	Always	13	3.42	Always	11.5
9. My school head handles conflicts constructively and do not take part of any gossip about my colleagues and other employees	3.83	Always	6	3.40	Always	13.5
10. My school head provides me with feedback concerning my performance.	3.87	Always	3.5	3.44	Always	8
11. My school head is a role model and sets a good example for the work group	3.93	Always	1	3.45	Always	5
12. My school head encourages me to participate in deciding how the work gets done	3.83	Always	6	3.46	Always	1.5
13. The school allows flexibility to arrange my work schedule to meet my personal/family responsibilities.	3.80	Always	10	3.40	Always	13.5
14. My school head allocates workload fairly and effectively.	3.90	Always	2	3.43	Always	9.5
15. The school foster settings that maximizes their competencies	3.87	Always	3.5	3.45	Always	5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.82	Always		3.43	Always	

The **school heads** of senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales recognized that indicator 11, my school head is a role model and sets a good example for the work group (WM=3.93, rank 1) always exist as indicators of human capital as teachers' working condition. The respondents always portrayed a role model quality for their senior high teachers and members of the school community, specifically setting a good example for the work group. The respondents are leaders in the new normal setting who led by example by positioning themselves as immense role models for the students, colleagues and parents. Hakansso & Adolfsson (2021); and Hansen, et al. (2019) pointed out that leadership skills and qualities can help advance career and lead to having greater overall job satisfaction and improved work conditions. For Dizon Jr., et al. (2021), as the school managers practice desirable and effective leadership skills, they can make themselves a viable candidate for higher roles to lead the school towards success.

Indicator 3, my school head treats me and my coworkers fairly; and 6, acknowledges the vulnerabilities of subordinates and actively hears their concerns obtained a WM of 3.73 (rank 14.5 respectively). Even these indicators were least from the rank, the school heads always treat their teachers and other staff fairly; acknowledges their weaknesses; and actively listens to their personal and professional concerns. This result also suggests that to improve vulnerabilities and weakness of teachers during the new normal, school heads need to display empathy and understanding of their teachers. In the upshot of COVID19 pandemic, Ducanes & Ocampo (2020) pointed out that effective leaders need to understand their nature and causes in order to sustain positive employee working condition. Overall, for the school heads, the human capital always exist as working condition at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales with OWM of 3.82 with Qualitative Rating of Always.

The **senior high school teachers** on the other hand recognized that indicator 1, my school head strongly considers my values and professional development goals; and 12, my school head encourages me to participate in deciding how the work gets done (WM=3.46, rank 1.5 respectively) always exist as indicators of human capital working condition. The teachers always observed and experienced that their school heads strongly regard their worth as senior high teacher and prioritizes professional development goals. This study of de Guzman & Villalobos (2023) emphasized the importance of a Department to further foster good working condition and environment for maximizing the level of job satisfaction among its educators.

Moreover, the DepEd Memorandum No. 291, s.2008, reiterated that effective principals maintain order in the school and classroom and appropriate condition; respond to teachers' concerns (personal and professional). Toropova, et al., (2021) and Mason & Poyatos Matas (2015 cited in Sims, 2020) examined human factor of work conditions and conclude that supervisor and colleagues play an important role in teachers' development.

Indicator 5, my school head cares about my opinions and suggestions obtained the least weighted mean of 3.36 (rank 15). The teachers always see and experience that their school heads cares about their insights, opinions and suggestions. Their respective school heads can provide leadership that affects every senior high teachers and students. They put forward leadership characteristics such as supportiveness, trusts and open-mindedness. Senior high school teachers are well considered of their intellectual contributions. Overall, the teachers perceived that human capital always exist as working condition at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales with OWM of 3.43 with Qualitative Rating of Always.

2.2. Social Capital

The **school heads** of senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales recognized that indicator 3, teachers are committed to education and welfare my students and sees to it that work is guided by a moral-ethical perspective; and 4, teachers are satisfied with the productivity and efficiency of team (WM=3.93, rank 1.5 respectively) always exist as indicators of social capital as teachers' working condition. The school heads always observed teachers' commitment to provide quality senior high school education and to assure the welfare of their senior high students and observance of high moral-ethical perspective at work. Moreover,

teachers in their work condition always observed work satisfaction and ethics, productivity and efficiency. According to Masoom (2021) and de Guzman & Villalobos (2023) teacher's commitment is the emotional bond teachers demonstrate toward their work and a critical factors in effective teaching.

Indicator 6, teachers home visits my students and talk to parents to communicate their children's performance and academic needs (least weighted mean of 3.60, rank 15). This indicator was also always observed by the school heads as indicator of social capital. They observed that senior high teachers conduct home visit of students; and talk and report to parents of their children's academic standing, performance their respective students' status and other academic needs. As a result, the students began to thrive in the senior high classroom, and the parents will further feel more connected to the school community this 'new normal' education set-up.

This type of social condition among teachers starts from the effort to promote parental involvement to her student's families and the teachers understand the relationship between pupils' home and school learning (Nkambule, 2022; and Chen, et al., 2022). Overall, the school heads perceived that social capital always exist as working condition at senior high schools of Division of Zambales with OWM of 3.80 with Qualitative Rating of Always.

Table 3: Level of Agreement of the School Heads and Senior High Teachers on the Existing Teachers' Working Condition as to Social Capital

Social Capital	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. The school head's personal style and character helped cultivate a climate and norm across the school community.	3.83	Always	6	3.44	Always	11
2. The school head encourages and guides the teachers in dealing with parents to identify their vulnerabilities and to address need for improvement.	3.90	Always	3	3.46	Always	5.5
3. I am committed to education and welfare of my students and sees to it that my work is guided by a moral-ethical perspective.	3.93	Always	1.5	3.50	Always	1
4. I am satisfied with the productivity and efficiency of my team	3.93	Always	1.5	3.41	Always	14
5. I genuinely listen and respect the opinions of my	3.87	Always	4.5	3.48	Always	2

colleagues and head by taking their views into account						
6. I home visit my students and talk to parents to communicate their children's performance and academic needs.	3.60	Always	15	3.43	Always	13
7. I have established rapport with other members of the workplace.	3.80	Always	8.5	3.45	Always	8
8. I reflect on how well my time is spent at work and assess my efficiency	3.80	Always	8.5	3.47	Always	3.5
9. My colleagues who are more experienced teachers provide support to new teachers.	3.80	Always	8.5	3.45	Always	8
10. My colleagues perceive that they have more control over some classroom practices	3.63	Always	14	3.40	Always	15
11. My workgroup looks for ways to change processes to improve productivity	3.77	Always	11.5	3.45	Always	8
12. My colleagues support each other for creative thinking and works for innovation	3.77	Always	11.5	3.44	Always	11
13. My colleagues work together and are dependent upon one another to achieve a common goal.	3.87	Always	4.5	3.44	Always	11
14. My colleagues exchange the information required for doing the work.	3.80	Always	8.5	3.46	Always	5.5
15. My colleagues' high performance in turn raises my performance level.	3.73	Always	13	3.47	Always	3.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.80	Always		3.45	Always	

The **teachers** at Senior High Schools of DepEd Division of Zambales recognized that indicator 3, teachers are committed to education and welfare my students and sees to it that my work is guided by a moral-ethical perspective (WM=3.50, rank 1) always exist as indicator of social capital working condition. This particular indicator was also always observed by their respective school head (see Table 8, WM=3.50, rank 1). An improved and acceptable teachers' working condition is when the heads and teachers themselves are committed to education and welfare and learning of their respective students; and when they work, they are guided by moral-ethical work values and principles.

Teachers were given the responsibility to foster among learners' the curiosity and creativity to become skillful and informed citizen (Deliquiña & de Guzman, 2021). Learners, to actually take charge of their education and study skills, teachers are there to facilitate variety, appropriate and effective instructional pedagogies and technologies (Calimlim, et al., 2022; and Werang & Leba, 2022).

Indicator 10, My colleagues perceive that they have more control over some classroom practices obtained the least weighted mean of 3.40 (rank 15). The senior high teachers believes that in the new normal setting, they should always observe and practice more control over some classroom, activities, routines and practices. According to Dizon Jr. (2021); Bactad, et al. (2021); and Werang & Leba (2022), this kind on social work condition will allow the smooth flow and execution of instructions and planned activities; acquisition of knowledge; and skills development in the different senior high school classes. Teachers must learn the most effective classroom management strategies to foster a desirable learning classroom condition and situation (Dizon Jr., et al., 2021). Overall, the teachers perceived that social capital always exist as working condition at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales with OWM of 3.45 with Qualitative Rating of Always.

2.3. Structural Capital

Table 4: Level of Agreement of the School Heads and Senior High Teachers on the Teachers' Working Condition as to Structural Capital

Structural Capital	School Heads			Senior High Teachers		
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
1. Conditions in my work area allow me to be highly productive.	3.80	Always	1.5	3.37	Always	5
2. I have the tools, supplies and equipment necessary to perform my job.	3.77	Always	3	3.27	Always	15
3. I have the flexibility to arrange my work schedule to meet my personal/family responsibilities	3.80	Always	1.5	3.35	Always	9.5
4. My supervisor provides me with the tools, supplies and equipment necessary to perform my job	3.70	Always	7	3.35	Always	9.5
5. There are sufficient classrooms to cater the student in every grade level.	3.60	Always	11.5	3.36	Always	7
6. The school has enough space for school activities and programs.	3.53	Always	13	3.36	Always	7

7. The school buildings adhere to building designs standards and structural soundness.	3.60	Always	11.5	3.32	Always	12
8. The classrooms are provided with needed furniture like teacher's table and chair, armchairs, desks, and cabinets.	3.67	Always	8.5	3.30	Always	13
9. The classroom is provided with lighting facilities, well ventilated, clean and organized	3.63	Always	10	3.36	Always	7
10. The school has an administrative office and room for DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) packages.	3.73	Always	5	3.44	Always	3
11. The Science/Math Room is equipped with instruments and equipment.	3.40	Always	15	3.28	Always	14
12. There are Library Resource Management and Development Canter, school clinic and school canteen.	3.47	Always	14	3.34	Always	11
13. The school gives me an opportunity to engage and challenge more of my students in a manageable way	3.67	Always	8.5	3.40	Always	4
14. I provide my students with interactive, engaging teaching environments to ensure effective learning.	3.73	Always	5	3.48	Always	1
15. I have set of routines in the preparations of my instructional materials.	3.73	Always	5	3.47	Always	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.66	Always		3.36	Always	

The **school heads** of senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales recognized that indicator 1, conditions in my work area allow me to be highly productive; and 3, teachers have the flexibility to arrange my work schedule to meet my personal/family responsibilities (WM=3.80, rank 1.5 respectively) always exist as indicators of structural capital as teachers' working condition. The school head respondents always observed that the structural capital working condition are high on having work area that will allow teachers to be highly productive

and senior high teachers can be flexible to arrange and balance their work schedule and personal/family roles and responsibilities. It was observed in the study of Allen, et al. (2021); Dizon, et al (2021); and Calimlim, et al. (2022) that being organized, for instance planning in advance the lessons, activities and tasks are vital aspects of a productive teacher. For Masom (2021), flexible working offers the teachers a healthy work-life balance and allows caretaking responsibilities.

Indicator 11, the Science/Math Room is equipped with instruments and equipment obtained the least weighted mean of 3.40 (rank 15). Although from the ranking, this indicator was least, this was believed by the school heads/principals to always exist aspect of structural capital. The Science/Math Room of senior high schools in the Division of Zambales is provided an/or equipped with instruments and equipment. Since in today's modern world, technology continuously affects man's everyday life. School administrators of Senior High School must equip teachers and students with Science/Math resources which they can best utilize and learn, a reason why innovation of school curriculum takes place and can lead to technological advancement in the future. Ortega & de Guzman, 2023; and Bunglo & de Guzman, 2023 emphasized the importance of nurturing learners' content, scientific and technological capabilities. Overall, the school heads perceived that structural capital always exist as working condition at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales with OWM of 3.66 with Qualitative Rating of Always.

On the other hand, the **senior high school teachers** acknowledged that indicator 14, the teachers provide my students with interactive, engaging teaching environments to ensure effective learning (WM=3.48, rank 1) always exist as indicator of structural capital working condition. The teachers always provide their students with collaborative, active and engaging environments to ensure effective learning. The very nature of Kto12 goals and objectives (Philippines Kto12 Program, Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013). The teachers always plan, execute and allow their students to be part of important learning activities and performance tasks to achieve further content and performance standards appropriate for senior high school levels stipulated in DepEd Memo 050 s.2020. The study of Wilson, et al. (2020) and Dizon Jr. (2021) showed that teachers provides their students a classroom setting to actively participate in processing and attaining knowledge and apply what they have discovered to solve problems. Planning and executing learning activities and allowing students the opportunities to further improve their competence are manifestations of structural capital of teacher's working condition.

Indicator 2, the teachers have the tools, supplies and equipment necessary to perform my job obtained the least weighted mean of 3.27 (rank 15). This indicator of structural capital is least observed and provided, however, the qualitative interpretation is still always. The schools always have the tools, supplies and equipment necessary to perform their job as teachers of their specific fields. According to Dizon, Jr. (2021) these tools are very necessary because aside from achieving content standards, senior high is also focused on developing competencies called performance standards. The inadequacy of available instructional materials can be a major concern in the basic education (Ortega & de Guzman, 2023; and Magsanop et al., 2022).

In adequacy can include the issues on funding, outdated materials, training and perceived importance (Sims, 2020; and Bunglo & de Guzman, 2023). Insufficiencies of these supply and resources can create significant obstacles to heads, teachers and students who attempt to meet mandated content and performance standards (Toropova, et al., 2021; and Manalili, et al., 2022). Overall, for the teachers, the structural capital always exist as working condition at senior high schools of DepEd Division of Zambales with OWM of 3. 3.36 with Qualitative Rating of Always.

Table 5: Summary on the Level of Agreement of the School Heads and Senior High School Teachers on the Teachers’ Working Condition

Teachers’ Working Conditions	School Heads			Senior High School Teachers		
	Overall Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank	Overall Weighted Mean	Qualitative Rating	Rank
Human Capital	3.82	Always	1	3.43	Always	2
Social Capital	3.80	Always	2	3.45	Always	1
Structural Capital	3.66	Always	3	3.36	Always	3
Grand Mean	3.76	Always		3.41	Always	

Human Capital gained the OWM=3.82 (rank 1st) interpreted as Always perceived. The school heads/principals Always perceived that the Working Condition existed at senior high schools in the Division of Zambales, primarily Human Capital. The Grand Mean was 3.76. On the teacher-respondents’, the Social Capital gained an OWM=3.45 (rank 1st) interpreted as Always, The teacher-respondents Always perceived that the Working Condition existed at senior high schools in the Division of Zambales, primarily Social Capital. The Grand Mean was 3.41. The school heads/principals always perceived that Human Capital exist as teachers’ working condition but for the senior high school teachers, it was Social Capital.

3. Analysis of Variance on the Difference in the Perception of Teachers’ Working Condition When Grouped According to the School Head Respondents’ Profile

Table 6: Summary in the Difference in the Perception of Teachers’ Working Condition when grouped according to the School Head Respondents’ Profile

Sources of Variations	Human Capital		Social Capital		Structural Capital	
	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.
Age	0.05	0.53	0.03	0.76	0.11	0.61
Gender	0.02	0.67	0.01	0.75	0.12	0.39
Highest Educational Attainment	0.08	0.43	0.09	0.34	0.17	0.35
Length of Service	0.06	0.62	0.06	0.55	0.10	0.71
Position/Designation	0.10	0.26	0.09	0.13	0.19	0.30
*Significant						

Human Capital. The significance values for age (0.53), gender (0.67), highest educational attainment (0.43), length of service (0.62), and position/designation (0.26) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference on the school heads’ perception. Their perceptions do not vary specifically in maintaining teachers’ human capital working condition even the respondents

differ in their personal profile. The school administrators who differ in aspect of their qualification and designation perceive and believe that effective principals maintain order in the classroom, respond to teachers' concerns, and provide relevant feedbacks.

Social Capital. The significance values for age (0.76), gender (0.75), highest educational attainment (0.34), length of service (0.55), and designation (0.13) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference on the school heads' perception. The school heads manifest similar understanding and knowledge on the aspects of social capital working conditions which need to be sustained and prioritized such as workgroup encouragement, having good relations with the principal, and conducive environment of the school.

Structural Capital. The significance values for age (0.61), gender (0.39), highest educational attainment (0.35), length of service (0.71), and designation (0.30) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference on the school heads' perception. The respondents have likeness of knowledge, observed and maintained teachers' structural working condition even the respondents differ in their personal profile.

4. Analysis of Variance on the Difference in the Perception of Teachers' Working Condition When Grouped According to Senior High Teachers' Profile

Table 7: Summary in the Difference in the Perception of Teachers' Working Condition when grouped according to the Senior High Teachers' Profile

Sources of Variations	Human Capital		Social Capital		Structural Capital	
	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.	Mean Square	Sig.
Age	0.08	0.87	0.23	0.42	0.15	0.64
Gender	0.48	0.17	0.01	0.32	0.45	0.16
Highest Educational Attainment	0.23	0.46	0.29	0.29	0.32	0.24
Length of Service	0.39	0.15	0.35	0.14	0.39	0.11
Position/Designation	0.17	0.62	0.07	0.88	0.06	0.91
<i>*Significant</i>						

Human Capital. The significance values for age (0.87), gender (0.17), highest educational attainment (0.46), length of service (0.15), and position (0.62) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference on the perception. The teachers have similarity of perception on the of observed and experienced human capital working condition even though they differ in their personal profile. According to Hakansso & Adolfsson (2021), the capacity of schools to improve teaching can be increased by guiding individual teachers and using systematic and meaningful evaluations and management by the organization.

Social Capital. The significance values for age (0.42), gender (0.32), highest educational attainment (0.29), length of service (0.14), and position/designation (0.88) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference on the perception. The respondents have similarity of perception on the

observed and experienced social capital working condition though the respondents vary in their personal profile.

Structural Capital. The significance values for age (0.64), gender (0.16), highest educational attainment (0.24), length of service (0.11), and position/designation (0.91) were higher than (0.05) alpha level of significance. Therefore, do not reject the hypothesis. There is no significant difference on the perception. There is similarity of observed and experienced structural capital working condition even the teacher-respondents vary in their personal profile. The participants manifest similarity of perception that the working condition of teachers is extremely important to them (Sims, 2020) and teachers are more satisfied and intend to stay longer in schools with a positive work environment.

5. Proposed Enhancement Program

Presented in Table/Matrix 17 is the proposed Enhancement Program which was designed aimed to further nurture the preferred school culture, improve teachers' working condition and basis for policy development at Senior High School in the Division of Zambales in the new normal. The Program was based on the findings of the present study specifically (1) preferred school culture element for senior high schools; and (2) theme/variable with the least results on senior high school teachers' working condition. The proposed Program is composed of six (6) aspects such as School Head Learn, School Head Do, Senior High Teacher Learn, Senior High Teacher Do, Time Frame, and Proposed Budget. To help make the Program more comprehensive and reliable, reviews of literature and related studies were also conducted by the researcher.

Table/Matrix 1

Proposed Enhancement Plan Aimed to Further Improve Teachers' Working Condition at Senior High School in the Division of Zambales in the New Normal

School Heads Learn	School Heads Do	SHS Teachers Learn	SHS Teachers Do	Time Frame (Target period of Implementation)	Proposed Budget (if necessary)
Building of teamwork and employee involvement and collaboration at SHS Division of Zambales	Conduct more activities (e.g., team building, strategic planning, culmination activity, re-echo, academic and sport competitions) to further employee engagement	Teamwork and teacher involvement and collaboration at Senior High Schools in the new normal	Participate in the conduct of activities (e.g., team building, strategic planning, culmination activity, re-echo, academic and sport competitions). Document the activities	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 65,000.00 MOOE
School-based merit and reward	Prioritize and implement regular school-based	Aspects, dimensions and/or	Improve, enhance and innovate to	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 45,000.00 MOOE

system at SHS in the Division of Zambales	merit and reward system for individual and group's exemplary outputs and achievements.	indicators of school-based merit and reward system for SHS	further efficacy, professional, accomplishments and standards in terms of instruction, resources production, research, linkages, trainings, and advanced education.		
Improvements, upgrades and innovations at SHS, Division of Zambales	Conduct of regular professional group conferences focused on presentation of innovative plans aims to further teachers' professional development and school improvement	Aspects school, personal and professional improvements, upgrades and innovations at SHS	Prepare personal and professional short and long term plans Prepare reports and documentations of outputs and participation in the activities	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 25,000.00 MOOE
Quality assurance and feedback mechanism for quality delivery of services to clients	Incorporate quality assurance and feedback mechanism to respective school to check and monitor quality in delivery of services to clients.	Quality assurance and feedback mechanism for quality teaching	Help in the utilization and implementation quality assurance and feedback mechanism in the senior high school in the normal. Document evidences of quality outputs/outcomes	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 25,000.00 MOOE
Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees and Code of Ethics for Professional	Conduct more INSET, LAC Sessions, Professional Group Conferences with the foremost objective to be more aware and uphold code of	Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees and Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers	Participate and show commitment in the conduct of INSET, LAC Sessions, Professional Group Conferences on Code of Ethics	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 25,000.00 MOOE

Teachers	ethics and ethical standards to help improve teachers' human and social capital working conditions		and Ethical Standards. Prepare reports and documentations of outputs and participation		
Involvement of teachers in planning and decision making with regards to instruction, school projects, and other important concerns	Devise a scheme in which senior high teachers will be more involved in planning and decision making on school projects, programs and concerns.	Specific aspects/ facets, and activities in planning, decision making and problem solving tasks	Respond to Memos and Orders in which teachers' expertise is sought Prepare reports and documentations of outputs and participation	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 10,000.00 MOOE
Equipment, materials and instruments necessary for SHS teachers to perform their job	Prioritize in the respective budget preparation the purchase of materials, instruments and equipment necessary for teachers to perform their tasks with efficacy.	Appropriate materials and instruments necessary to perform job during the resumption of full face-to-face	Lead and manifest high level of content and technological pedagogical knowledge Utilization of equipment and instruments for teaching and learning in the new normal	October 2023 – Dec. 2026	Php 55,000.00 MOOE

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that:

1. Majority of the senior high school heads are male middle aged adults, Master's degree holders with doctorate units, Principal II, and works for two and a half decades while majority of the senior high school teachers are female young adults, baccalaureate degree holders with Master's units, Teacher II and have been serving as professional teachers for less than a decade.
2. The teachers' working condition that always exist at school based on school heads perception was human capital most expressly on having a school head who is a role model for the work group while the teachers' working condition that always exist at school, based on the teachers' perception was social capital focused on commitment on education and towards moral-ethical perspective on work.

3. There is no significant difference in the perception on teachers' working condition when grouped according to school head respondents' profile.
4. There is no significant difference in the perception on teachers' working condition when grouped according to teachers' profile.
5. An Enhancement Plan was formulated aimed to better improve teachers' working condition and consideration for policy implementation at Senior High Schools in the Division of Zambales.

Recommendations

In the light of the foregoing conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were advanced:

1. Senior High School administrators in the Division of Zambales may conduct regular planning activities and learning action cells (LACs) focused on presentation of plans and innovation aims to further maintain continuous professional and school improvements.
2. Senior High School administrators and teachers in the Division of Zambales may incorporate quality assurance and feedback mechanism to check and monitor quality in delivery of services to clients.
3. Administrators of DepEd Schools Division of Zambales may conduct more conferences/forums and learning action cells (LACs) with the objective of consistently uphold the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees and Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers and to help improve teachers' human and social capital working conditions in the new normal.
4. Senior High School administrators in the Division of Zambales may prioritize respective budgets/income in the purchase of instruments and equipment necessary for senior high teachers to perform their job.
5. Present the developed Enhancement Program to the School Heads, Supervisors and Education Specialist/Curriculum Planners of DepEd Division of Zambales for review, and consideration for policy implementation focused on the teachers' working conditions.
6. Conduct a follow up study outside the Division of Zambales to confirm the findings of the present study.

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